

ISic3086

I.Sicily inscription 3086

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331401

1. [έκοιμήθ]η □ τῆ πρό □ ις' καλ [— — —]
2. [ύπ(ατία) Θεοδ]οσίου □ τὸ ιβ' □ καὶ Β[αλεντινιανοῦ τὸ β'].
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645437

PHI 331401

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0842

Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*. 28-29: 3-29. At 17 no.55 fig.2a

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